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Title: Study on mycotoxin contamination of maize kernels in Spain

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Abstract: Mycotoxins are secondary metabolites produced mainly by fungal species belonging to the genera *Fusarium*, *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* and belong to the most relevant contaminants of food and feed. Cereals are the main source of mycotoxins in the diet. The most prominent mycotoxins are aflatoxins B₁, B₂, G₁ and G₂ (AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁ and AFG₂), fumonisins B₁ and B₂ (FB₁ and FB₂), ochratoxin A (OTA), zearalenone (ZEA), deoxynivalenol (DON), 3- and 15-acetyl-deoxynivalenol (3- and 15-ADON), and T-2 and HT-2 toxins. Maximum levels allowed in food are very different depending on mycotoxin and food type, consumer susceptibility and current legislation in each country. Among cereals, maize and its derivatives deserve special attention. The present study was designed to investigate the occurrence of these mycotoxins in Spanish maize kernels collected in different regions for a five-year period (2015-2019) using a multi-mycotoxin UPLC-MS/MS method. Ninety-eight samples of maize kernels collected in 26 Spanish grain stores were ground to fine powder, extracted with acetonitrile-water-formic acid (80:19:1, v/v/v), centrifuged and analyzed by UPLC-ESI-MS/MS using matrix-matched calibration. The method was validated and mean recovery rates were 83-103.4% and mean relative standard deviations ranged from 4.1 to 8.5%. FB₁, FB₂, DON, 3-ADON, ZEA, AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₂, T-2 and HT-2 toxins were detected at levels higher than their respective limits of quantification in 71.4%, 56.2%, 31.6%, 5.02%, 24.5%, 9.2%, 9.2%, 2%, 5.1% and 5.1% of maize kernel samples, respectively. OTA was not detected. Among the positive samples, 20.4%, 5.1%, 3%, and 3% had levels exceeding the European Union permissible limits for FB₁+FB₂, ZEA, AFB₁, and total aflatoxins, respectively. Co-occurrence of various mycotoxins (two to seven) in the same sample at quantifiable levels was observed in 33.5% of samples being the association of FB₁, FB₂ and DON the most frequent, followed by the presence of FB₁, FB₂, ZEA and DON.

*Highlights (for review)

Highlights

A study on mycotoxin contamination of maize grain was performed in Spain (2015-2019)

Multiple mycotoxins in maize were determined by a validated UPLC-ESI-MS/MS method

Good results for repeatability, reproducibility and recovery were achieved

Fumonisin were quantified in 60–73% of samples from each year

Mycotoxin co-occurrence (two-seven) at quantifiable levels was observed in 33.5% of samples

1 **Study on mycotoxin contamination of maize kernels in Spain**

2

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13 **Abstract**

14 Mycotoxins are secondary metabolites produced mainly by fungal species
15 belonging to the genera *Fusarium*, *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* and belong to the
16 most relevant contaminants of food and feed. Cereals are the main source of
17 mycotoxins in the diet. The most prominent mycotoxins are aflatoxins B1, B2,
18 G1 and G2 (AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁ and AFG₂), fumonisins B1 and B2 (FB₁ and
19 FB₂), ochratoxin A (OTA), zearalenone (ZEA), deoxynivalenol (DON), 3- and
20 15-acetyl-deoxynivalenol (3- and 15-ADON), and T-2 and HT-2 toxins.

21 Maximum levels allowed in food are very different depending on mycotoxin and
22 food type, consumer susceptibility and current legislation in each country.

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24 study was designed to investigate the occurrence of these mycotoxins in
25 Spanish maize kernels collected in different regions for a five-year period (2015-
26 2019) using a multi-mycotoxin UPLC-MS/MS method. Ninety-eight samples of
27 maize kernels collected in 26 Spanish grain stores were ground to fine powder,
28 extracted with acetonitrile-water-formic acid (80:19:1, v/v/v), centrifuged and
29 analyzed by UPLC-ESI-MS/MS using matrix-matched calibration. The method
30 was validated and mean recovery rates were 83–103.4% and mean relative
31 standard deviations ranged from 4.1 to 8.5%. FB₁, FB₂, DON, 3-ADON, ZEA,
32 AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₂, T-2 and HT-2 toxins were detected at levels higher than
33 their respective limits of quantification in 71.4%, 56.2%, 31.6%, 5.02%, 24.5%,
34 9.2%, 9.2%, 2%, 5.1% and 5.1% of maize kernel samples, respectively. OTA
35 was not detected. Among the positive samples, 20.4%, 5.1%, 3%, and 3% had
36 levels exceeding the European Union permissible limits for FB₁+FB₂, ZEA,
37 AFB₁, and total aflatoxins, respectively. Co-occurrence of various mycotoxins
38 (two to seven) in the same sample at quantifiable levels was observed in 33.5%
39 of samples being the association of FB₁, FB₂ and DON the most frequent,
40 followed by the presence of FB₁, FB₂, ZEA and DON.

41 **Keywords:** mycotoxins; Spanish maize; UPLC-MS/MS; co-occurrence,

42 1. Introduction

43 Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is an important cereal crop worldwide and in Spain,
44 where its production has fluctuated substantially in recent years. Maize is
45 produced all over the country but mainly in the regions Castile and Leon,
46 Aragon, and Extremadura followed by Catalonia, Castile-La Mancha, Navarre,
47 Andalusia and Galicia (Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Medio Ambiente,
48 2019). Maize in Spain is used mainly for animal feed as forage or in the
49 manufacture of combined feedstuffs and in small proportion in the manufacture
50 of food products destined to human consumption (corn flakes, corn flour, corn
51 meal, corn oil, baby food, and starch) (Escobar et al., 2013) or even for direct
52 consumption in salads or as corncob.

53 Various phytopathogenic fungal species infect maize in nature. In addition to
54 crop losses produced by these fungi, they can synthesize mycotoxins either
55 pre- or post-harvest, which can persist in manufactured by-products. The
56 occurrence of mycotoxins in maize kernels is of great concern worldwide, and is
57 often associated with mycotoxicosis in livestock and in humans (Logrieco, Mulè,
58 Moretti, & Bottalico, 2002). The main mycotoxins found in maize are aflatoxins
59 (AFs), fumonisins (FUM), type-A and type-B trichothecenes, zearalenone
60 (ZEA), zearalenol, moniliformin, beauvericin and fusaproliferins. The main AFs
61 are aflatoxin B1, B2, G1, and G2 (AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁, and AFG₂). AFB₁ is
62 genotoxic and immunosuppressive in animals and is a potent hepatocarcinogen
63 (IARC, 2002). AFB₁, AFG₁ and the mixture of AFs have been classified by the
64 International Agency of Research on Cancer as Group 1 carcinogens (IARC,
65 1993). Other important groups of mycotoxins commonly found in maize
66 encompass the fumonisins, especially, fumonisin B1 (FB₁), accepted as
67 possible carcinogenic to humans (Group 2B) (IARC, 2002), and fumonisin B2
68 (FB₂) (Kamle, Mahato, Devi, Lee, Kang, & Kumar, 2019). The type-A
69 trichothecenes, among them the highly toxic T-2 and HT-2 toxins (T-2 and HT-
70 2) have also been reported in maize grains (Schollenberger et al., 2012). The
71 type-B trichothecenes, like deoxynivalenol (DON), its 3- and 5-acetyl derivatives
72 (3-ADON and 15-ADON), nivalenol (NIV), and other toxigenic metabolites like
73 zearalenone (ZEA), zearalenol, moniliformin, beauvericin and fusaproliferins are
74 also frequent contaminants of maize (Jestoi, 2008; Logrieco et al., 2002).

75 However, ochratoxin A (OTA), a mycotoxin that possesses nephrotoxic,
76 teratogenic, immunotoxic and possibly neurotoxic properties, and classified as
77 possibly carcinogenic to humans in Group 2B (IARC, 2002), is scarcely reported
78 in maize.

79 Production of FUM, trichothecenes and ZEA in maize is attributed mainly to
80 *Fusarium verticillioides* (FUM), *F. proliferatum* (FUM), *F. solani* (FUM), *F.*
81 *fujikuroi* (FUM), *F. graminearum* (DON and 3-ADON/15-ADON or NIV, ZEA), *F.*
82 *crookwellense* (DON, ZEA), *F. sporotrichioides* (type-A trichothecenes), *F.*
83 *culmorum* (DON, ZEA/type-A trichothecenes), and *F. equiseti* (NIV/ZEA/T-2)
84 (Leslie & Summerell, 2006; Schollenberger et al., 2012). AFs are produced
85 mainly by strains of *Aspergillus flavus* (AFB₁ and AFB₂), and *A. parasiticus*
86 (AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁, and AFG₂). Other *Aspergillus* species (*A. ochraceus*, *A.*
87 *steynii*, and *A. westerdijkiae*) can produce OTA (Frisvad, Frank, Houbroken,
88 Kuijpers, & Samson, 2004; Gil-Serna, Vázquez, Sardiñas, González-Jaen, &
89 Patiño, 2011). Strains of *A. niger* isolated from maize may be OTA and/or FUM
90 producers (Frisvad et al., 2011).

91 The occurrence of toxigenic fungi and mycotoxins in crops depends mainly
92 on agricultural practices, genetic factors, insect damage, storage conditions
93 and, especially, on the climatic conditions, which are now under the climatic
94 change scenario (Battilani et al., 2016; Magan & Aldred, 2007; Mateo, Valle-
95 Algarra, Jiménez, & Magan, 2013; Moretti, Pascale, & Logrieco, 2019;
96 Tarazona, Mateo, Gómez, Romera, & Mateo, 2020). Mycotoxin occurrence in
97 maize in Spain has been scarcely studied (Ariño, Juan, Estopañan, &
98 González-Cabo, 2007; Castellá, Bragulat & Cabañes, 1999; Jaimez, Fente,
99 Franco, Cepeda & Vázquez, 2004; Muñoz, Cardelle, Pereiro, & Riguera, 1990)
100 and recent information in the context of climate change is not available.

101 Co-occurrence of various mycotoxins in maize samples even when they are
102 produced by different fungal species is a relevant issue due to possible
103 interactions among them (Abbas, Cartwright, Xie, & Shier, 2006; Franco, Petta,
104 Rottinghaus, Bordin, Gomes, & Oliveira, 2019; IARC, 2003; Kovalsky et al.,
105 2016; Mahdjoubi, Arroyo-Manzanares, Hamini-Kadar, García-Campaña,
106 Mebrouk, & Gámiz-Gracia 2020; Moreno et al., 2009). The toxicity of such
107 mycotoxin mixtures is difficult to be predicted based on their individual toxicities
108 and exposure to these combinations can lead to additive, synergistic or

109 antagonistic toxic effects (Grenier & Oswald, 2011).

110 The analytical methodology for mycotoxin analysis in food has been reviewed
111 (Malachová et al., 2018; Valle-Algarra, Mateo-Castro, Mateo, Gimeno-
112 Adelantado, & Jiménez, 2014). Methods such as enzyme-linked immunosorbent
113 assay (Okuma, Huynh, & Hellberg, 2018), gas chromatography
114 (Schollenberger, Müller, Rühle, Suchy, Planck, & Drochner, 2005; Valle-Algarra,
115 Medina, Gimeno-Adelantado, Llorens, Jiménez, & Mateo, 2005), or liquid
116 chromatography with fluorescence or mass spectrometry detection (LC-MS/MS)
117 (Köppen, Koch, Siegel, Merkel, Maul & Nehls, 2010; Lattanzio, Solfrizzo,
118 Powers, & Visconti, 2007; Sulyok, Berthiller, Krska, & Schuhmacher, 2006;
119 Sulyok, Krska, & Schuhmacher, 2007) have been used. In the last few years,
120 the availability of ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC or
121 UPLC), coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS/MS), or time-of-
122 flight mass spectrometry (UHPLC-ToF-MS) using electrospray ionization (ESI)
123 or atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) has enabled the
124 development of sensitive, selective and accurate methods for mycotoxin
125 determination (Malachová et al., 2014). These methods can reduce limitations
126 of classic LC methods, such as lengthy clean-up procedures, derivatization of
127 analytes, peak interference and long retention times (Arroyo-Manzanares,
128 Huertas-Pérez, García-Campaña, & Gámiz-Gracia, 2014; Romera, Mateo,
129 Mateo-Castro, Gómez, Gimeno-Adelantado, & Jiménez, 2018; Silva, Brites,
130 Pouca, Barbosa, & Freitas, 2019). These methods, due to the high specificity
131 and sensitivity of mass spectrometry, have the possibility of detect/quantify low
132 levels of many mycotoxins even in complex matrices in the same
133 chromatographic run (multi-mycotoxin analysis) thus avoiding spending time in
134 the analysis of groups of mycotoxins. There are problems related to matrix
135 effects and isobaric interferences that are not completely resolved. Matrix
136 effects caused by the suppression/enhancement of the analyte signal during the
137 ionization process can affect the repeatability and accuracy of the method,
138 leading to incorrect results (Sulyok et al., 2006; Varga et al., 2012). Various
139 approaches (sample dilution, matrix-matched calibration, standard addition or
140 internal calibration with stable isotopically labeled compounds) have been used
141 to overcome these difficulties (Varga et al., 2012). The last approach uses ¹³C-
142 labeled mycotoxins as internal standards and has been claimed to have good

143 accuracy and reproducibility (Zhang et al., 2017) although it has the problem of
144 the high costs of the internal standards and availability for all the mycotoxins of
145 interest (De Santis et al., 2017; Li, Steimling, Konschnik, Grossman, & Kahler,
146 2019). Perhaps, the most commonly used procedure is matrix-matching
147 calibration, especially when the matrix is the same and blank samples
148 concerning the analytes of interest are available. Signal suppression effects
149 were investigated for mycotoxins in maize and in other cereals (Sulyok et al.,
150 2006; 2007) and it was concluded that matrix-matched calibration should be
151 performed taking into account the particular matrix.

152 There is little information on the presence of mycotoxins in maize harvested
153 and commercialized in Spain. The aim of the present study was to investigate
154 and evaluate the occurrence of regulated or intended to be regulated
155 mycotoxins in the European Union (European Commission, 2006a; 2007; 2013)
156 in maize kernels harvested throughout the Spanish geography and
157 commercialized in stores located in different regions of Spain from 2015 to 2019
158 using an optimized UPLC–MS/MS method.

159 **2. Materials and methods**

160 *2.1. Samples*

161 Ninety-eight samples of maize kernels without visible signs of mold growth
162 were collected in the years 2015–2019 in 26 grain stores located in different
163 Spanish regions according to the procedures given in Commission Regulation
164 (EC) No 401/2006 (European Commission, 2006b). Aggregated samples (about
165 500 g after reduction) were analyzed as soon as they reached the laboratory or
166 were stored at –20 °C until analysis.

167 *2.2. Chemicals and reagents*

168 Mycotoxin standards of AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁, AFG₂, DON, 3-ADON, OTA, ZEA,
169 FB₁, FB₂, HT-2 and T-2 toxins were supplied by Sigma (Sigma–Aldrich,
170 Alcobendas, Spain). Formic acid and ammonium formate were purchased from
171 Panreac (Castellar del Valles, Spain). Acetonitrile (MeCN) and methanol were
172 purchased from J.T. Baker (Deventer, the Netherlands). All solvents were LC
173 grade. Pure water was obtained from a Milli-Q apparatus (Millipore, Billerica,

174 MA, USA) and was used when water was required.

175 *2.3. Preparation of standard solutions*

176 Each standard was dissolved in MeCN at a concentration of 1000 µg/mL and
177 stored at –20 °C in a sealed vial until use. Working standards were prepared by
178 appropriate dilution of known volumes of the stock solution with MeCN–water
179 and used to obtain calibration curves. Standard solutions of individual
180 mycotoxins were prepared from stock solutions at different concentrations:
181 AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁, AFG₂, OTA (10 µg/mL) and DON, T-2, HT-2, 3-ADON, ZEA,
182 FB₁ and FB₂ (100 µg/mL) using MeCN-water (75:25, v/v). The stock solutions
183 were stored in the dark at –20 °C. More diluted individual standards of these
184 mycotoxins were prepared when needed for recovery assays. A stock standard
185 solution mixture of mycotoxins was prepared from individual standard solutions
186 in MeCN–water (75:25, v/v) and stored at –20 °C. The concentrations of each
187 mycotoxin (ng/mL) in the mixture were AFB₁ (200), AFB₂ (200), AFG₁ (200),
188 AFG₂ (200), ZEA (10000), OTA (2600), DON (25000), 3-ADON (10000), FB₁
189 (25000), FB₂ (12500), T-2 (2500), and HT-2 (2500). Variable volumes of this
190 solution were further added to blank maize extracts before injection into the
191 chromatographic system. These solutions were appropriately diluted with the
192 solvent before addition to blank maize samples to estimate the limits of
193 detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ).

194 *2.4. Sample preparation*

195 Samples of maize kernels were finely ground and carefully mixed to achieve
196 complete homogenization and extracted as described by Romera et al. (2018).
197 Briefly, each subsample (2 g) was placed into a Falcon tube and extracted with
198 8 mL of MeCN-water-formic acid (80:19:1, v/v/v) by shaking in orbital shaker
199 (Infors-HTAerotron, Bottminghen, Switzerland). Extracts were centrifuged (4260
200 g, 5 min) and did not undergo any cleanup. Two mL of the supernatant of each
201 extract was filtered using a syringe filter (0.22 µm, PTFE), diluted with the same
202 volume of solvent and an aliquot was injected into the UPLC-MS/MS system.

203 *2.5. Determination of mycotoxins by UPLC–MS/MS*

204 Chromatographic separation and mass detection was performed as
205 described by Romera et al. (2018). The instrument was an ACQUITY UPLC™
206 system (Waters, Manchester, UK), equipped with an electrospray ionization
207 interface used in positive mode (ESI+) and an ACQUITY TQD tandem
208 quadrupole mass spectrometer (Waters Co., Milford, MA, USA). Separation was
209 carried out in a reversed-phase ACQUITY UPLC BEH C18 column (50 × 2.1
210 mm, 1.7 µm particle size) (Waters). Thirty µL was injected. Column and
211 autosampler temperatures were set at 25 °C and 15 °C, respectively. The
212 mobile phase consisted of a mixture of (A) water containing ammonium formate
213 (0.15 mmol/L) and formic acid (0.1%) and (B) methanol at a flow-rate of 0.37
214 mL/min using a gradient elution program (Romera et al., 2018). The MS/MS
215 conditions appear in Table 1. Masslynx 4.1™ software (Waters, Manchester,
216 UK) was used for data acquisition and processing. Mean retention times (t_R)
217 (2.5% tolerance) and the two most intense transitions of the parent compound
218 were monitored and selected for identification (Table 1). Only the most intense
219 peak (quantifier) was used for quantification while the other peak (qualifier) was
220 considered for identification. The quantifier/qualifier ion ratios were measured in
221 the chromatograms of the samples and used as an additional confirmation
222 criterion (De Santis et al., 2017; European Commission, 2002; SANTE, 2017).

223 2.6. Calibration and method validation

224 For calibration purposes, matrix-matched calibration was performed using
225 blanks samples previously analyzed and containing undetectable levels of the
226 studied mycotoxins. Calibration curves were obtained by linear regression of the
227 chromatographic peak areas from the quantifier ions *versus* the concentration of
228 each mycotoxin standard in extracts of blank maize. Weighted linear regression
229 (weighting factor = $1/x$) was considered for calculation of calibration lines.
230 Linearity was assumed when $R^2 > 0.99$ and residuals were $< 20\%$. For each
231 mycotoxin, LOD in the injected solution was estimated as $3.3 \times s/b$ where s was
232 the standard error of the estimate and b is the slope of a calibration line
233 obtained by using samples containing the standards at low levels, near the LOD
234 and LOQ, while LOQ was estimated as $10 \times s/b$ (ICH, 2005). The dilution ratio
235 was considered to calculate the LOD and LOQ of the method. Trueness was
236 based on recovery values. Validation was carried out for each analyte by

237 spiking a milled, homogenized blank maize sample at four levels (LOQ, 2×LOQ,
238 5×LOQ, and 10×LOQ) in five replicates each level with variable volumes of
239 standard solutions of mycotoxins. The spiked samples (2 g) were let stand
240 overnight at 40 °C to allow the solvent to evaporate; then they were extracted
241 and analyzed as previously indicated for maize samples. For each mycotoxin,
242 the percent recovery and the relative standard deviation of recovery at each
243 spiking level (RSD), as well as the mean % recovery and mean RSD were
244 calculated.

245 *2.7. Determination of mycotoxins in samples*

246 Mycotoxins in samples were identified by their t_R and by the presence of the
247 quantifier and qualifier ions in the MRM mass spectrum. Concentrations were
248 calculated by interpolation of the peak area corresponding to the quantifier ion
249 in the calibration lines. When the signal was too large for the linear calibration
250 range, an aliquot of the extract was further appropriately diluted with the same
251 solvent and analyzed again and the extraction/dilution procedure was
252 considered. Two calibration mixtures (standards added to matrix) at high and
253 low levels with regard to calibration curves were included as controls with each
254 batch of analyzed samples.

255 **3. Results and discussion**

256 *3.1. Method validation*

257 Figs. 1 and 2 show UPLC-(ESI+)-MS/MS MRM chromatograms of mycotoxin
258 standards added to extracts of blank maize samples at the given levels. The
259 letters Q and q identify the peaks obtained by monitoring the quantifier and the
260 qualifier ion, respectively. The residuals in calibration curves obtained by
261 weighted regression were <25%, and linearity was assumed since the R^2 values
262 were >0.99. The method was validated in-house based on a) recovery rate of
263 spiked blank samples at the levels indicated for each analyte (Section 2.6); b)
264 RSD of mycotoxin concentrations determined in the spiked samples at these
265 levels. The LOD and LOQ of the studied mycotoxins determined in spiked blank
266 maize samples, the mean extraction recovery rates and the mean RSD under
267 repeatability conditions (RSD_r) of recoveries appear in Table 2. The mean

268 recovery rates were in the range of 63.0 to 103.4%, and the RSD_r of the
269 recoveries ranged from 4.1 to 8.5%. They were considered acceptable and both
270 fulfilled the performance criteria established in SANTE (2017). The LOQ values
271 are below the EU regulatory limits in maize for all the analytes under the study.

272 3.1. Analysis of maize samples

273 The summarized results of the analysis of the maize samples in the five-year
274 period using the validated method with the concentrations of the different
275 mycotoxins are in Table 3. Table 4 lists the number of samples analyzed every
276 year, the number of positive samples (containing mycotoxin levels equal or
277 higher than their respective LOQ) as well as their means and ranges of
278 concentrations throughout the studied period. Fig. 3 illustrates MRM
279 chromatograms of some mycotoxins found in maize samples.

280 3.1.1. Aflatoxins

281 Nine samples contained AFB₁ and/or AFB₂ and two others contained AFG₂ at
282 levels higher or equal than their LOQ. Three samples showed AFB₁ levels (22.0
283 and 124.1 ng/g in 2017, and 80.3 ng/g in 2018) that exceeded the EU maximum
284 limits for AFB₁ in maize (Table 4). The median of these AFs was quite low
285 compared with the mean (Table 3). The sample contaminated with the highest
286 AFB₁ content was taken in 2017 in Zaragoza (Aragon), a region located in the
287 Ebro river valley that has hot, sunny and dry summers (30–35 °C). AFG₁ was
288 detected only in four samples always at levels <LOQ and AFG₂ was found at
289 levels >LOQ in two samples in 2018 and 2019. Occurrence of AFs in maize in
290 other countries of Southern Europe has been reported and levels changed over
291 the years depending on the weather conditions. Thus, Pietri, Bertuzzi, Pallaroni,
292 and Piva (2004) analyzed 503 Italian maize samples in the period 1995–1999
293 and found that AFB₁ means ranged from 0.3 to 4.10 ng/g. In the period 2005–
294 2011, AFB₁ was detected every year in maize fields at harvest (range of
295 positive samples, 10–41%, range of means, 7–42 ng/g, level range <LOD–560
296 ng/g) (Battilani, Camardo Leggieri, Rossi, & Giorni, 2013). In Croatia, 31.4% of
297 972 maize samples analyzed in 2009–2013 contained AFB₁ (mean 38.46 ng/g,
298 maximum 2072 ng/g) (Pleadin, Vulić, Perši, Škrivanko, Capek, & Cvetnić,
299 2015). In Greece, in the period 2010–2013, AFs were found in 17.5% of maize

300 samples at levels >10 ng/g (range 0.6–45.2 ng/g) (Manouras & Malissiova,
301 2018). In Serbia, Kos et al. (2018) detected AFs in 5.0–72.3% of the 3000
302 maize samples collected during 2012–2016. Gruber-Dorninger, Jenkins, and
303 Schatzmayr (2019) reviewed the status of global contamination of maize with
304 mycotoxins in the period 2008–2017. According to this review, 24% of 15889
305 maize samples were contaminated with AFB₁ worldwide (median 4 ng/g, max.
306 6105 ng/g) and AFB₁ was more prevalent in Southern Europe than in other
307 European regions. AFB₁ was also prevalent and detected at high levels often
308 exceeding the EU regulatory limits in Sub-Saharan Africa, Southeast Asia, and
309 South Asia. In China, Sun et al. (2011) reported 100% AFB₁ incidence (range
310 0.4–136.8 ng/g). The climate of Southern Europe countries, characterized by
311 high temperatures and high humidity (high water activity, a_w), can favor the
312 growth of *A. flavus* and *A. parasiticus* and AF production. Giorni, Magan, Pietri,
313 Bertuzzi, & Battilani (2007) reported optimal growth at 25–30 °C and 0.99 a_w ,
314 with maximal AF production around 25 °C and 0.99 a_w . However, a change
315 towards slightly high temperatures has occurred in the last years as Abdel-Hadi,
316 Schmidt-Heydt, Parra, Geisen, and Magan (2012) found that *A. flavus* grows
317 optimally at 30–35 °C whereas AF production is optimal at 25–35 °C. AFB₁
318 levels also depend on variables such as “year”, “sampling place” and the
319 interaction between both factors (Battilani et al., 2012). Weather changes during
320 the pre- and post-harvest greatly affect AF content of maize. According to
321 predictive models related to climate change the risk for AFB₁ contamination in
322 maize is likely to increase in Europe in the next 30 years (increase of +2 °C
323 scenario) because this variation may favor *A. flavus* growth and AF production
324 (Battilani et al., 2016; Moretti et al., 2019). Further treatments of maize kernels
325 to produce by-products intended for human consumption may decrease initial
326 levels, although AFs are very stable to thermal treatments. Ibañez-Vea,
327 Martínez, González-Peñas, Lizarraga, and López de Cerain (2011) found AFB₁
328 in 9% of corn-based breakfast cereals collected in Spain at levels <0.2 ng/g.
329 After comparison with occurrence in other countries, especially those in
330 Southern Europe, AF contamination of maize kernels does not seem to be a
331 worrying issue in Spain although some non-compliant samples may appear in
332 surveys as shown in the present study. Therefore, routine monitoring of AFs in
333 maize should be encouraged in future.

334 3.1.2. DON and 3-ADON

335 The percentage of samples with quantifiable DON concentrations was 31.6%
336 and the prevalence of samples with detectable levels was 40% (Table 3). The
337 mean was 421.7 ng/g, the median 180 ng/g, and no level exceeded the EU
338 maximum limit. DON was quantified every year of the period and the highest
339 incidence at levels \geq LOQ occurred in 2016 (68%) although the highest annual
340 mean concentration (881 ng/g) was reached in 2018 (Table 4). Only 5.1% of the
341 samples showed quantifiable levels of 3-ADON+15-ADON (Table 3). No EU
342 maximum limits exist for the acetyl derivatives of DON. In previous work, DON
343 was detected in Spanish maize grown in Galicia in the range 43–315 ng/g
344 (Muñoz et al., 1990). DON has been highly reported in maize (Palumbo et al.,
345 2020). Gruber-Dorninger et al. (2019) have reported that 67% of maize samples
346 worldwide were contaminated with DON (median 520 ng/g, max. 51374 ng/g).
347 Levels were higher in Central than in Southern Europe and values peaked in
348 these regions in 2014 (mean around 2000 ng/g) although means decreased
349 below 500 ng/g in 2015–2017, which agrees with our results. In Italy, Pietri et al.
350 (2004) reported a mean value of 860 ng/g with a range of <20 to 9357 ng/g and
351 Camardo Leggieri et al. (2020) found that 56% of maize fields grown in the
352 region of Emilia Romagna were contaminated with DON (mean 479 ng/g),
353 although three samples exceeded the EU limit. Other country located in
354 Southern Europe where DON was detected in maize is Croatia (85% positive
355 samples, mean 2150 ng/g, range 15–17920 ng/g) (Pleadin, Sokolovic, Persi,
356 Zadravec, Jaki, & Vulic, 2012). In Central Europe, DON was detected in maize
357 collected in many countries. It was detected in Poland (mean 50.77 ng/g, range
358 <LOD–90.54 ng/g) (Czembor, Stępień & Waśkiewicz, 2015), in Austria, where
359 Berthiller et al. (2009) found DON in 54 maize samples (range 42–3680 ng/g),
360 while 43 and 6 samples contained 15-ADON and 3-ADON, respectively, and in
361 the Netherlands, Belgium, France, and Germany, during 2003–2007 (range of
362 means in maize silage 273–1476 ng/g) (Van Asselt et al., 2012). In Northern
363 Serbia, DON was detected in most samples over the period 2012–2015 but the
364 year-to-year incidence was variable associated to weather and reached 100%
365 in 2014 in the range 428–16350 ng/g (Kos et al., 2020). The results of the
366 present study show that contamination of maize seeds with these
367 trichothecenes in Spain is not severe but deserves monitoring.

368 3.1.3. ZEA

369 In the studied period, ZEA was quantified in 24.5% of samples and was
370 detected in other 11% samples (Table 3). Six samples surpassed the EU
371 maximum limit (European Commission, 2007). The maximum concentration
372 was found in a sample from Galicia in 2016, a year with high prevalence (45.5%
373 positive samples) and mean of 1493 ng/g (Table 4). Jaimez et al. (2004)
374 detected ZEA at very low levels (range 0.47–2.24 ng/g) in Spanish maize. With
375 regard to other countries in Southern Europe, Pietri et al. (2004) in Italy reported
376 a range of <LOD to 2531 ng/g. The worldwide occurrence of ZEA in maize has
377 been reviewed (Gruber-Dorninger et al., 2019; Maragos, 2010; Palumbo et al.,
378 2020). In Europe, contamination of maize varied with years even in a given
379 country/region and mean levels ranged from 456 ng/g in 1996 to 13 ng/g in
380 1998 (Maragos, 2010). In Germany, ZEA was found in 27% of the samples
381 analyzed in 2006 (mean 70 ng/g) and in 93% of samples analyzed in 2007
382 (mean 480 ng/g) (EFSA, 2011). Gruber-Dorninger et al. (2019) reported that
383 44% of maize samples analyzed worldwide during the years 2008–2017 were
384 positive for ZEA (median 77 ng/g, max. 16495 ng/g) and mean level peaked in
385 2014, as reported for DON in central and Southern Europe. The results of the
386 present study show that ZEA concentrations in Spanish maize are comparable
387 to those in other countries of Europe, but deserve monitoring because of the
388 occurrence of non-compliant samples.

389 3.1.4. *FB₁* and *FB₂*

390 The most common mycotoxins found in maize in the present study were *FB₁*
391 and *FB₂*. For the five-year period, the overall mean and median levels of
392 *FB₁*+*FB₂* were 5734 ng/g and 1306 ng/g, respectively. The levels of *FB₁*+*FB₂*
393 exceeded the EU limit for maize in 20.4% of samples (Table 3). Fig. 4 shows
394 the distribution of the levels of *FB₁*+*FB₂* in 70 samples with quantifiable
395 concentrations of *FB₁* or *FB₂*. Most of the non-compliant samples were in the
396 4000-5000 ng/g range. The median value of FUM over the five-year study
397 period is in agreement with the global median for FUM reported in the review of
398 Gruber-Dorninger et al. (2019). However, in this review, FUM levels in maize of
399 up to 218883 ng/g are reported. In our study, the highest value was found in a
400 sample with a *FB₁*+*FB₂* level of 6.31×10^4 ng/g. Levasseur-Garcia, Bailly,

401 Kleiber and Bailly (2015) studied 117 maize samples from Italy, Denmark,
402 France, Hungary, The Netherlands, and Poland and found that 26% of them
403 exceeded the EU maximum level and the mean was 2509 ng/g. Fumonisin
404 also occur in maize from other countries located in Southern Europe. Thus, in
405 Portugal, reported levels for FB₁+FB₂ by Lino et al. (2006) (mean 460 ng/g, max
406 1162 ng/g) or by Silva et al. (2019) (range of positives, 134-1044 ng/g) are
407 lower than those found by us. In various countries of Southern Europe
408 (Portugal, Spain, Italy, Serbia, Greece and Turkey), Rodrigues and Nachrer
409 (2012) reported that 90% of surveyed maize samples were positive for FUM
410 with a mean value of 2271 ng/g. In Croatia, Domijan, Peraica, Jurjević, Ivić, and
411 Cvjetković (2005) found FB₁ in 100% of 49 analyzed samples (mean 459.8
412 ng/g, range 142.2–1377.6 ng/g). In Northern Italy, all maize samples surveyed
413 by Pietri et al. (2004) in a five-year study contained FB₁ (overall mean 3064
414 ng/g, range 53–51690 ng/g, % samples > 5000 ng/g, 16.9). In our study, the
415 high mean value is due mainly to three samples with exceptionally high levels of
416 FB₁+FB₂ (> 4.5 x 10⁴ ng/g) (Fig. 4). The remaining samples showed levels
417 similar to those found by these authors. Samples tested for FUM by Berardo,
418 Lanzanova, Locatelli, Laganà, Verderio, and Motto (2011) during 2006-2008
419 averaged 7200 ng/g (range <75–77000 ng/g) and 64% of the samples
420 exceeded 4000 ng/g, although a large inter-year variation was noticeable.
421 Likewise, in Northern Italy, Camardo Leggieri, Lanubile, Dall'Asta, Pietri and
422 Battilani (2020) have reported a FUM range of 1718–106054 ng/g in freshly
423 harvested maize samples (year 2014); moreover, 90% of samples showed FUM
424 levels above the legal limit. In Turkey, high FUM levels were found (mean
425 88240 ng/g, range 800–356800 ng/g) (Oruc, Cengiz & Kalkanli, 2006). FUM
426 occurrence in maize is also a relevant issue in other parts of the world. In the
427 USA, Abbas et al. (2006) found FB₁ in maize (mean 40400 ng/g, range 12100–
428 75000 ng/g). In Brazil, usually all the samples were contaminated with FUM and
429 levels >4000 ng/g and up to 66274 ng/g have been registered (De Souza et al.,
430 2013; Oliveira, Rocha, Sulyok, Krska, & Mallmann, 2017). High levels have
431 been reported in Northeastern Iran (50% incidence, mean 223640 ng FB₁/g) by
432 Alizadeh et al. (2012). FUM incidence is very high in Sub-Saharan Africa (Abia
433 et al., 2013; Kamala et al., 2016; Manizan et al., 2018). Regarding our study,
434 although some samples of Spanish maize kernels contained high levels of

435 FB₁+FB₂ (>4000 ng/g), the concentrations of these mycotoxins are generally
436 similar to those found in other countries.

437 Table 4 lists the concentrations of fumonisins in the samples in every year of
438 the studied period. The highest average levels were recorded in the samples
439 collected in 2016 and 2017 and the lowest in the samples collected in 2015 and
440 2019. The year-to-year prevalence of FUM ranged from 60% in 2015 to 73% in
441 2017. FUM contamination of maize and its by-products is a concerning issue in
442 countries located in the Mediterranean basin (Logrieco et al., 2002; Marín,
443 Ramos, Cano-Sancho, & Sanchis, 2012). In Spain, there is very little
444 information on this problem. Castellá et al. (1999) found that 87.3 % of Spanish
445 analyzed maize samples contained FB₁+FB₂ (mean 5600 ng/g, range 200–
446 24900 ng/g); that mean agrees with the mean level found in the present study in
447 spite of the different years monitored but differ from data of Monbaliu et al.
448 (2010) who reported ranges from 61 to 5114 ng FB₁/g and from <LOQ to 1527
449 ng FB₂/g in maize samples from Spain collected in 2008. Cao et al. (2014)
450 found that about 60% of the samples from maize hybrid plants grown in Galicia
451 (Spain) during 2007–2009 showed FUM levels in the range 20–27800 ng/g.
452 García-Díaz, Gil-Serna, Vázquez, Botia, & Patiño (2020) evaluated the
453 presence of FUM and their producing species along maize production cycle in
454 three different stages (anthesis, harvest and storage) in the South Area of the
455 Community of Madrid and observed the highest levels of FUM in pre-harvest in
456 2017, where some samples exceeded the EU limits, which was attributed to the
457 humid and hot weather at pre-harvest time. These results agree with those
458 found in the present study. Ariño et al. (2007, 2009) also found that FUM
459 occurrence increases along the stages of maturation of maize in field and is
460 higher in conventional than in transgenic maize. All these studies suggest that
461 the accumulation of FUM in maize grains is progressive, reaching the highest
462 levels in the store. Therefore, overall FUM occurrence can be considered as a
463 worrying issue in maize worldwide so that regular monitoring and measures to
464 diminish their levels are needed.

465 3.1.5. OTA

466 OTA was not detected in the samples analyzed in the present study. Low or
467 lack of incidence of OTA in maize is in agreement with studies performed in

468 other countries (Binder, Tan, Chin, Handl, & Richard, 2007; Hajok, Kowalska,
469 Piekut, & Ćwieląg-Drabek, 2019; Kirinčič, Škrjanc, Kos, Kozolc, Pirnat, &
470 Tavčar-Kalcher, 2015; Kos et al., 2020; Manizan et al., 2018; Mudili et al., 2014;
471 Streit, Naehrer, Rodrigues & Schatzmayr, 2012). Global occurrence in maize in
472 the period 2008–2017 is scarce (5% incidence, median 3 ng/g, max. 889 ng/g)
473 and in Central and Southern Europe, the mean values are usually below 5 ng/g
474 (Gruber-Dorninger et al., 2019). The results obtained in this study indicate that
475 OTA occurrence in Spanish maize kernels cannot be considered a threatening
476 issue.

477 3.1.6. *T-2 and HT-2 toxins*

478 T-2 and HT-2 toxins were detected in 25 and 23 samples, respectively (Table
479 3). Both occurred at levels > LOQ in five samples (in 2017, 2018 and 2019)
480 (Table 4) although the maximum level (26.8 ng/g) was below the EU maximum
481 recommended level for T-2+HT-2 (European Commission, 2013). Low amounts
482 of these trichothecenes in maize grain from Spain were also found by Cano-
483 Sancho et al. (2011), Marín et al. (2012) and Park et al. (2018). According to the
484 review of Gruber-Dorninger et al. (2019), 12% of maize analyzed worldwide
485 showed detectable levels of T-2 (median 25 ng/g, max. 978 ng/g) although the
486 overall mean levels were <10 ng/g in countries located in Southern Europe
487 along 2015–2017, in agreement with our results. From our study, it may be
488 assumed that these toxins in maize kernels do not constitute a worrying issue at
489 present in Spain.

490 3.2. *Co-occurrence of mycotoxins*

491 Fig 5 shows the year-to-year co-occurrence of different mycotoxins at
492 quantifiable levels in the analyzed maize samples. Two or more mycotoxins co-
493 contaminated 33.7% of the studied samples. In some cases, they occurred at
494 levels exceeding the individual EU limits. A year-to-year variation of the
495 mixtures of mycotoxins in a given sample can be observed. Usually two
496 mycotoxins could be quantified in the same sample (16 binary combinations,
497 48.5%) but up to seven mycotoxins were also found at levels \geq LOQ for each
498 mycotoxin. The most usual binary combination was FUM (FB₁ either alone or
499 with FB₂)+DON (eight binary combinations) but these toxins also co-occurred

500 in other eight combinations of up to seven mycotoxins (Fig. 5). The ternary
501 combination FUM+DON+ZEA appeared in six samples, five of them in the year
502 2016. Other common combination was DON+ZEA usually associated with other
503 mycotoxins (13 samples). FUM+ZEA co-occurred in two samples as a binary
504 combination but also in 13 combinations with other mycotoxins. A sample
505 showing the highest AFB₁+AFB₂ level was also contaminated with >6×10⁴ ng/g
506 of FB₁+FB₂. Another sample containing 80.9 ng/g of AFB₁+AFB₂ also contained
507 5800 ng/g of FB₁+FB₂. Although samples may contain only relatively low levels
508 of each individual mycotoxin, co-occurrence of different mycotoxins has been
509 reported frequently in maize, other cereals and feed samples. Crops (among
510 them maize) may be infested with multiple strains of mycotoxigenic fungi and
511 since fungal strains can produce more than one type of mycotoxin, co-
512 contamination of feed and mycotoxin co-exposure of consumers is the rule not
513 the exception (Gruber-Dorninger et al., 2019; Palumbo et al., 2020). Thus,
514 according to Streit et al. (2012), 46% of maize samples were co-contaminated
515 with two or more mycotoxins which generally agrees with our results and with
516 those from other researchers (Camardo Leggieri et al., 2020; Franco et al.,
517 2019; Kamala et al., 2016; Kos et al., 2020; Mahdjoubi, et al., 2020, Pereira et
518 al., 2014). The simultaneous occurrence of ZEA and DON in corn silage has
519 been reported (Tangni, Pussemier, & Van Hove, 2013). Arroyo-Manzanares,
520 Rodríguez-Estévez, Arenas-Fernández, García-Campaña and Gámiz-Gracia
521 (2019) have found that most of the 227 Spanish swine feed samples collected
522 in 2017 were co-contaminated with two or more (up to eight) mycotoxins (not
523 always regulated) so that 69% of samples contained 3–5 mycotoxins, being
524 quaternary mixtures the most frequent. Among the 127 mycotoxin combinations
525 reported for cereals and derived cereal products in the review of Smith, Madec,
526 Coton, and Hymery (2016), AF+FUM, DON+ZEA, AF+OTA, and FUM+ZEA
527 were the most common. Since OTA was not detected, the AF+OTA combination
528 was not found in the present study. Most frequently observed combinations in
529 maize worldwide were those of *Fusarium* mycotoxins DON, ZEA, and FUM
530 (Gruber-Dorninger et al., 2019). The co-occurrence of different mycotoxins
531 within the same food or feed sample may result in a change of the toxicity to
532 humans and animals due to possible antagonistic, additive or synergistic effects
533 (Alassane-Kpembi, Schatzmayr, Taranu, Marin, Puel & Oswald, 2017; Grenier

534 & Oswald, 2011). This issue deserves more research tasks in future, which may
535 be relevant to clarify if there is a need for regulation of mycotoxin mixtures in
536 feed (Gruber-Dorninger et al., 2019).

537 **4. Conclusions**

538 A sensitive, rapid, and reliable UPLC–(ESI+)–MS/MS multi-mycotoxin
539 method using matrix-matched calibration for the determination of target
540 mycotoxins in maize kernels was validated and applied to study the distribution
541 of most of the mycotoxins regulated (or intended to be regulated in the EU) in
542 maize kernels collected in 26 stores across different Spanish regions
543 throughout the years 2015 to 2019. Until now any survey has been performed
544 covering all the Spanish regions and the present study has revealed that maize
545 grains are susceptible to contamination by various regulated and non-regulated
546 mycotoxins. FB₁, FB₂, DON, 3-ADON, ZEA, AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₂, T-2 and HT-2
547 were quantified in 71.4%, 56.2%, 31.6%, 5.02%, 24.5%, 9.2%, 9.2%, 2%, 5.1%
548 and 5.1% of samples, respectively. The maximum EU allowable limits for
549 FB₁+FB₂, ZEA, AFB₁, and AFB₁+AFB₂, were exceeded in 20.4%, 5.1%, 3%,
550 and 3% of the analyzed samples, respectively. OTA was not detected and the
551 sum of T-2+HT-2 was below the EU recommended limit. Various mycotoxins
552 co-occurred at levels \geq LOQ in about 34% of the samples, which may increase
553 toxicity due to possible additive or synergistic effects. The results obtained in
554 this study contribute to increase the knowledge on mycotoxin contamination of
555 maize grain consumed in Spain. In view of the results of the present study and
556 those obtained by other authors, a large surveillance task is needed to avoid
557 that the most toxic mycotoxins from highly contaminated maize samples could
558 carry over feed and food products ready for animal or human consumption.

559 **Declaration of competing interest**

560 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or
561 personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported
562 in this paper.

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570 **References**

571 Abbas, H. K., Cartwright, R. D., Xie, W., & Shier, W. T. (2006). Aflatoxin and
572 fumonisin contamination of corn (maize, *Zea mays*) hybrids in Arkansas.
573 *Crop Protection*, *25*, 1-9.

574 Abdel-Hadi, A., Schmidt-Heydt, M., Parra, R., Geisen, R., & Magan, N. (2012).
575 A systems approach to model the relationship between aflatoxin gene
576 cluster expression, environmental factors, growth and toxin production by
577 *Aspergillus flavus*. *Journal of The Royal Society Interface*, *9*, 757–767.

578 Abia, W. A., Warth, B., Sulyok, M., Krska, R., Tchana, A. N., Njobeh, P. B., et
579 al. (2013). Determination of multi-mycotoxin occurrence in cereals, nuts and
580 their products in Cameroon by liquid chromatography tandem mass
581 spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). *Food Control*, *31*, 438–453.

582 Alassane-Kpembi, I., Schatzmayr, G., Taranu, I., Marin, D., Puel, O., & Oswald,
583 I. P. (2017). Mycotoxins co-contamination: Methodological aspects and
584 biological relevance of combined toxicity studies. *Critical Reviews in Food
585 Science and Nutrition*, *57*, 3489e3507.
586 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2016.1140632>.

587 Alizadeh, A. M., Roshandel, G., Roudbarmohammadi, S., Roudbary, M.,
588 Sohanaki, H., Ghiasian, S. A., et al. (2012). Fumonisin B1 contamination of
589 cereals and risk of esophageal cancer in a high risk area in northeastern
590 Iran. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention*, *13*, 2625–2628.

591 Ariño, A., Juan, T., Estopañan, G., & González-Cabo J. F. (2007). Natural
592 occurrence of *Fusarium* species, fumonisin production by toxigenic strains,
593 and concentrations of fumonisins B1 and B2 in conventional and organic
594 maize grown in Spain. *Journal of Food Protection*, *70*, 151–156.

595 Ariño, A., Herrera, M., Juan, T., Estopañan, G., Carramiñana, J. J., Rota, C., et

596 al. (2009). Influence of agricultural practices on the contamination of maize
597 by fumonisin mycotoxins. *Journal of Food Protection*, 72, 898–902.

598 Arroyo-Manzanares, N., Huertas-Pérez, J. F., García-Campaña, A. M., &
599 Gámiz-Gracia, L. (2014). Simple methodology for the determination of
600 mycotoxins in pseudocereals, spelt and rice. *Food Control*, 36, 94–101.

601 Arroyo-Manzanares, N., Rodríguez-Estévez, V., Arenas-Fernández, P., García-
602 Campaña, A. M., & Gámiz-Gracia, L. (2019). Occurrence of mycotoxins in
603 swine feeding from Spain. *Toxins*, 11, 342.
604 <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins11060342>.

605 Battilani, P., Camardo Leggieri, M., Rossi, V., & Giorni, P. (2013). AFLA-maize,
606 a mechanistic model for *Aspergillus flavus* infection and aflatoxin B1
607 contamination in maize. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 94, 38-46.

608 Battilani, P., Toscano, P., Van der Fels-Klerx, H., Moretti, A., Leggieri, M. C.,
609 Brera, C., et al. (2016). Aflatoxin B1 contamination in maize in Europe
610 increases due to climate change. *Scientific Reports*, 6, 24328;
611 [doi:10.1038/srep24328](https://doi.org/10.1038/srep24328).

612 Berthiller, F., Dall’asta, C., Corradini, R., Marchelli, R., Sulyok, M., Krska, R., et
613 al. (2009). Occurrence of deoxynivalenol and its 3-β-D-glucoside in wheat
614 and maize. *Food Additives and Contaminants*, 26, 507-511.

615 Binder, E. M., Tan, L. M., Chin, L. J., Handl, J., & Richard, J. (2007). Worldwide
616 occurrence of mycotoxins in commodities, feeds and feed ingredients.
617 *Animal Feed Science and Technology*, 137, 265–282.

618 Camardo Leggieri, M., Lanubile, A., Dall’Asta, C., Pietri, A., & Battilani, P.
619 (2020). The impact of seasonal weather variation on mycotoxins: maize crop
620 in 2014 in northern Italy as a case study. *World Mycotoxin Journal*, 13, 25-
621 36.

622 Cano-Sancho, G., Valle-Algarra, F. M., Jiménez, M., Burdaspal, P., Legarda, T.
623 M., Ramos, A. J., et al. (2011). Presence of trichothecenes and co-
624 occurrence in cereal-based food from Catalonia (Spain). *Food Control*, 22,
625 490–495.

626 Cao, A., Santiago, R., Ramos, A. J., Souto, X. C., Aguín, O., Malvar, R. A., et

627 al. (2014). Critical environmental and genotypic factors for *Fusarium*
628 *verticillioides* infection, fungal growth and fumonisin contamination in maize
629 grown in northwestern Spain. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*,
630 177, 63–71.

631 Castellá, G., Bragulat, M. R., & Cabañes, F. J. (1999). Surveillance of
632 fumonisins in maize-based feeds and cereals from Spain. *Journal of*
633 *Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 47, 4707–4710.

634 Czembor, E., Stępień, Ł., & Waśkiewicz, A. (2015). Effect of environmental
635 factors on *Fusarium* species and associated mycotoxins in maize grain
636 grown in Poland. *PLoS ONE* 10, e0133644.
637 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0133644>.

638 De Santis, B., Debegnach, F., Gregori, E., Russo, S., Marchegiani, F., Moracci,
639 G., et al. (2017). Development of a LC-MS/MS method for the multi-
640 mycotoxin determination in composite cereal-based samples. *Toxins*, 9, 169.
641 <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins9050169>.

642 De Souza, M. L. M., Sulyok, M., Silva, O. F., Costa, S. S., Brabet, C.,
643 Machinski Junior, M., et al. (2013). Cooccurrence of mycotoxins in maize
644 and poultry feeds from Brazil by liquid chromatography/tandem mass
645 spectrometry. *The Scientific World Journal*, Article ID 427369, 9 pp.
646 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2013/427369>.

647 Domijan, A. M., Peraica, M., Jurjević, Z., Ivić, D., & Cvjetković, B. (2005).
648 Fumonisin B1, fumonisin B2, zearalenone and ochratoxin A contamination of
649 maize in Croatia. *Food Additives and Contaminants*, 22, 677–680.

650 EFSA (2011). Scientific Opinion on the risks for public health related to the
651 presence of zearalenone in food. *EFSA Journal*, 9, 1–124.

652 Escobar, J., Lorán, S., Giménez, I., Ferruz, E., Herrera, M., Herrera, A., et al.
653 (2013). Occurrence and exposure assessment of *Fusarium* mycotoxins in
654 maize germ, refined corn oil and margarine. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*,
655 62, 514–520.

656 European Commission (2002). Commission Decision 2002/657/EC of 12
657 August 2002 implementing council directive 96/23/EC concerning the

658 performance of analytical methods and the interpretation of results. *Official*
659 *Journal of the European Communities*, L 221, 8–36.

660 European Commission (2006a). Commission Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 of
661 19 December 2006 setting maximum levels for certain contaminants in
662 foodstuffs. *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 364, 5–24.

663 European Commission (2006b). Commission Regulation (EC) No 401/2006 of
664 23 February 2006 laying down the methods of sampling and analysis for the
665 official control of the levels of mycotoxins in foodstuffs. *Official Journal of the*
666 *European Union*, L 70, 12–34.

667 European Commission (2007). Commission Regulation (EC) No 1126/2007 of
668 28 September 2007 amending Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 setting
669 maximum levels for certain contaminants in foodstuffs as regards Fusarium
670 toxins in maize and maize products. *Official Journal of the European Union*,
671 L 255, 14–17.

672 European Commission (2013). Commission Recommendation of 27 March
673 2013 on the presence of T-2 and HT-2 toxin in cereals and cereal products
674 (2013/165/EU). *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 91, 12–15.

675 Franco, L. T., Petta, T., Rottinghaus, G. E., Bordin, K., Gomes, G. A., &
676 Oliveira, C. A. F. (2019). Co-occurrence of mycotoxins in maize food and
677 maize-based feed from small-scale farms in Brazil: a pilot study. *Mycotoxin*
678 *Research*, 35, 65–73.

679 Frisvad, J. C., Frank, J. M., Houbraken, J. A. M. P., Kuijpers, A. F. A., &
680 Samson, R. A. (2004). New ochratoxin A producing species of *Aspergillus*
681 section *Circumdati*. *Studies in Mycology*, 50, 23–43.

682 Frisvad, J. C., Larsen, T. O., Thrane, U., Meijer, M., Varga, J., Samson, R. A.,
683 et al. (2011). Fumonisin and ochratoxin production in industrial *Aspergillus*
684 *niger* strains. *PLoS ONE*, 6, e23496.
685 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0023496>.

686 García-Díaz, M., Gil-Serna, J., Vázquez, C, Botia, M. N., & Patiño, B. (2020). A
687 Comprehensive study on the occurrence of mycotoxins and their producing
688 fungi during the maize production cycle in Spain. *Microorganisms*, 8, 141.

689 <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8010141>.

690 Gil-Serna, J., Vázquez, C., Sardiñas, N., González-Jaén, M. T., & Patiño, B.
691 (2011). Revision of ochratoxin A production capacity by the main species of
692 *Aspergillus* section *Circumdati*. *Aspergillus steynii* revealed as the main risk
693 of OTA contamination. *Food Control*, 22, 343–345.

694 Giorni, P., Magan, N., Pietri, A., Bertuzzi, T., & Battilani, P. (2007). Studies on
695 *Aspergillus* section *Flavi* isolated from maize in northern Italy. *International*
696 *Journal of Food Microbiology* 113, 330–338

697 Grenier, B., & Oswald, I. (2011). Mycotoxin co-contamination of food and feed:
698 meta-analysis of publications describing toxicological interactions. *World*
699 *Mycotoxin Journal*, 4, 285e313. <https://doi.org/10.3920/WMJ2011.1281>.

700 Gruber-Dorninger, C., Jenkins, T. & Schatzmay, G. (2019). Global mycotoxin
701 occurrence in feed: a ten-year survey. *Toxins*, 11, 375.
702 <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins11070375>.

703 Hajok, I., Kowalska, A., Piekut, A., & Ćwieląg-Drabek, M. (2019). A risk
704 assessment of dietary exposure to ochratoxin A for the Polish population.
705 *Food Chemistry*, 284, 264–269.

706 Ibañez-Vea, M., Martínez, R., González-Peñas, E., Lizarraga, E., & López de
707 Cerain, A. (2011). Co-occurrence of aflatoxins, ochratoxin A and
708 zearalenone in breakfast cereals from Spanish market. *Food Control*, 22,
709 1949–1955.

710 ICH (International Conference on Harmonization) (2005). Validation of
711 analytical procedures: text and methodology Q2(R1).
712 https://database.ich.org/sites/default/files/Q2_R1_Guideline.pdf. Accessed
713 14 June 2019.

714 International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC). (1993). IARC
715 monographs on the evaluation of carcinogenic risks to humans, Vol. 56.
716 Some naturally occurring substances: food items and constituents,
717 heterocyclic aromatic amines and mycotoxins, (pp. 245–395). Lyon: IARC
718 Press.

719 International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC). (2002). IARC

720 monographs on the evaluation of carcinogenic risks to humans, Vol. 82.
721 Some traditional herbal medicines, some mycotoxins, naphthalene and
722 styrene (pp. 301-366). Lyon: IARC Press.

723 Jaimez, J., Fente, C. A., Franco, C.M., Cepeda, A., & Vázquez B. I. (2004). A
724 survey of the fungal contamination and presence of ochratoxin A and
725 zearalenone on Spanish feed and raw materials. *Journal of the Science of*
726 *Food and Agriculture*, 84, 832–840.

727 Jestoi, M. (2008). Emerging *Fusarium*–mycotoxins fusaproliferin, beauvericin,
728 enniatins, and moniliformin: a review. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and*
729 *Nutrition*, 48, 21–49.

730 Jindal, N., Mahipal, S. K., & Rottinghaus, G. E. (1999). Occurrence of fumonisin
731 B1 in maize and poultry feeds in Haryana, India. *Mycopathologia*, 148, 37–
732 40.

733 Kamala, A., Kimanya, M., Haesaert, G., Tiisekwa, B., Madege, R., Degraeve,
734 S., et al. (2016). Local post-harvest practices associated with aflatoxin and
735 fumonisin contamination of maize in three agro ecological zones of
736 Tanzania. *Food Additives and Contaminants: Part A*, 33, 551-559,

737 Kamle, M., Mahato, D. K., Devi, S., Lee, K. E, Kang, S. G., & Kumar, P. (2019).
738 Fumonisin: Impact on agriculture, food, and human health and their
739 management strategies. *Toxins*, 11, 328.
740 <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins11060328>.

741 Kirinčič, S., Škrjanc, B., Kos, N., Kozolc, B., Pirnat, N., & Tavčar-Kalcher, G.
742 (2015). Mycotoxins in cereals and cereal products in Slovenia–Official
743 control of foods in the years 2008-2012. *Food Control*, 50, 157–165.

744 Köppen, R., Koch, M., Siegel, D., Merkel, S., Maul, R., & Nehls, I. (2010).
745 Determination of mycotoxins in foods: current state of analytical methods
746 and limitations. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 86, 1595-1612.

747 Kos, J., Hajnal, E. J., Malachová, A., Steiner, D., Stranska, M., Krska, R., et al.
748 (2020). Mycotoxins in maize harvested in Republic of Serbia in the period
749 2012–2015. Part 1: Regulated mycotoxins and its derivatives. *Food Control*,
750 312, 126034.

- 751 Kos, J., Hajnal, E. J., Šarić, B., Jovanov, P., Mandić, A., Đuragić, O. et al.
752 (2018). Aflatoxins in maize harvested in the Republic of Serbia over the
753 period 2012–2016. *Food Additives and Contaminants: Part B*, 11, 246-255.
- 754 Kovalsky, P., Kos, G., Nährer, K., Schwab, C., Jenkins, T., Schatzmayr, G., et
755 al. (2016). Co-occurrence of regulated, masked and emerging mycotoxins
756 and secondary metabolites in finished feed and maize-an extensive survey.
757 *Toxins*, 8, 363. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins8120363>
- 758 Lattanzio, V. M. T., Solfrizzo, M., Powers, S., & Visconti, A. (2007).
759 Simultaneous determination of aflatoxins, ochratoxin A and *Fusarium* toxins
760 in maize by liquid chromatography/tandem mass spectrometry after
761 multitoxin immunoaffinity cleanup. *Rapid Communications in Mass*
762 *Spectrometry*, 21, 3253–3261.
- 763 Leslie, J. F., & Summerell, B. A. (2006). *The Fusarium Laboratory Manual*, Vol.
764 1, 1st ed.; Hoboken, NJ: Wiley-Blackwell.
- 765 Levasseur-Garcia, C., Bailly, S., Kleiber, D. & Bailly, J. D. (2015). Assessing
766 risk of fumonisin contamination in maize using near-infrared spectroscopy.
767 *Journal of Chemistry*, 2015; 485864, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2015/485864>
- 768 Li, D., Steimling, J. A., Konschnik, J. D., Grossman, S. L., & Kahler, T. W.
769 (2019). Quantitation of mycotoxins in four food matrices comparing stable
770 isotope dilution assay (SIDA) with matrix-matched calibration methods by
771 LC–MS/MS. *Journal of AOAC International*, 102, 1673-1680.
- 772 Lino, C. M., Silva, L. J. G., Pena, A. L. S., & Silveira, M. I. (2006).
773 Determination of fumonisins B1 and B2 in Portuguese maize and maize-
774 based samples by HPLC with fluorescence detection. *Analytical and*
775 *Bioanalytical Chemistry*, 384, 1214–1220.
- 776 Logrieco, A., Mulè, G., Moretti, A., & Bottalico, A. (2002). Toxigenic *Fusarium*
777 species and mycotoxins associated with maize ear rot in Europe. *European*
778 *Journal of Plant Pathology*, 108, 597–609.
- 779 Magan, N., & Aldred, D. (2007). Post-harvest control strategies: Minimizing
780 mycotoxins in the food chain. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*,
781 119, 131–139.

- 782 Mahdjoubi, C. K., Arroyo-Manzanares, N. Hamini-Kadar, N., García-Campaña,
783 A. M., Mebrouk, K., & Gámiz-Gracia, L. (2020). Multi-mycotoxin occurrence
784 and exposure assessment approach in foodstuffs from Algeria *Toxins*, *12*,
785 194. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins12030194>.
- 786 Malachová, A., Stránská, M., Václavík ová, M.,
787 Elliott, C. T., Black, C., Meneely J., et al. (2018). Advanced LC–MS-based
788 methods to study the co-occurrence and metabolization of multiple
789 mycotoxins in cereals and cereal-based food. *Analytical and Bioanalytical*
790 *Chemistry*, *410*, 801–825.
- 791 Malachová, A., Sulyok, M., Beltrán, E., Berthiller, F., & Krska, R. (2014).
792 Optimization and validation of a quantitative liquid chromatography–tandem
793 mass spectrometric method covering 295 bacterial and fungal metabolites
794 including all regulated mycotoxins in four model food matrices. *Journal of*
795 *Chromatography A*, *1362*, 145-156.
- 796 Manizan, A. L., Oplatowska-Stachowiak, M., Piro-Metayer, I., Campbell, K.,
797 Koffi-Nevry, R., Elliott, C., et al. (2018). Multi-mycotoxin determination in rice,
798 maize and peanut products most consumed in Cote d'Ivoire by UHPLC-
799 MS/MS. *Food Control*, *87*, 22–30.
- 800 Manouras, A. & Malissiova, E. (2018). Occurrence of aflatoxins in compound
801 feeds and feed materials for dairy livestock in Central Greece. *Journal of the*
802 *Hellenic Veterinary Medical Society*, *66*, 169-176.
- 803 Maragos, C. M. (2010). Zearalenone occurrence and human exposure. *World*
804 *Mycotoxin Journal*, *3*, 369-383.
- 805 Marín, S., Ramos, A. J., Cano-Sancho, G., & Sanchis, V. (2012). Reduction of
806 mycotoxins and toxigenic fungi in the Mediterranean basin maize chain.
807 *Phytopathologia Mediterranea*, *51*, 93–118.
- 808 Mateo, E. M., Valle-Algarra, F. M., Jiménez, M., & Magan, N. (2013). Impact of
809 three sterol-biosynthesis inhibitors on growth of *Fusarium langsethiae* and
810 on T-2 and HT-2 toxin production in oat grain under different ecological
811 conditions. *Food Control*, *34*, 521–529.
- 812 Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación, 2019. Avances - Superficies y

813 producciones de cultivos.
814 [https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-](https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/cuaderno_septiembre2019_tcm30-521414.pdf)
815 [agrarias/cuaderno_septiembre2019_tcm30-521414.pdf](https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/cuaderno_septiembre2019_tcm30-521414.pdf). Accessed 30
816 November 2019.

817 Monbaliu, S., Van Poucke, C., Detavernier, C., Dumoulin, F., Van De Velde,
818 M., Schoeters, E., et al. (2010). Occurrence of mycotoxins in feed as
819 analyzed by a multi-mycotoxin LC-MS/MS method. *Journal of Agricultural*
820 *and Food Chemistry*, 58, 66–71.

821 Moretti, A., Pascale, M., & Logrieco, A. F. (2019). Mycotoxin risks under a
822 climate change scenario in Europe. *Trends in Food Science and*
823 *Technology*, 84, 38–40.

824 Mudili, V., Siddaih, C. N., Nagesh, M., Garapati, P., Kumar, K. N., Murali, H. S.,
825 et al. (2014). Mould incidence and mycotoxin contamination in freshly
826 harvested maize kernels originated from India. *Journal of the Science of*
827 *Food and Agriculture*, 94, 2674–2683.

828 Muñoz, L., Cardelle, M., Pereiro, M., & Riguera, R. (1990). Occurrence of corn
829 mycotoxins in Galicia (Northwest Spain). *Journal of Agricultural and Food*
830 *Chemistry*, 38, 1004–1006.

831 Okuma, T. A., Huynh, T. P., & Hellberg, R. S. (2018). Use of enzyme-linked
832 immunosorbent assay to screen for aflatoxins, ochratoxin A, and
833 deoxynivalenol in dry pet foods. *Mycotoxin Research*, 34, 69.
834 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12550-017-0300-3>.

835 Oliveira, M. S., Rocha, A., Sulyok, M., & Krska, R. (2017). Mallmann natural
836 mycotoxin contamination of maize (*Zea mays* L.) in the South region of
837 Brazil. *Food Control*, 73, 127–132.

838 Oruc, H. H., Cengiz, M., & Kalkanli, O. (2006). Comparison of aflatoxin and
839 fumonisin levels in maize grown in Turkey and imported from the USA.
840 *Animal Feed Science and Technology*, 128, 337–341.

841 Palumbo, Crisci, R. A., Venâncio, A., Cortiñas Abrahantes, J., Dorne, J. L.,
842 Battilani, P., et al. (2020). Occurrence and co-occurrence of mycotoxins in
843 cereal-based feed and food. *Microorganisms*, 8, 74;

- 844 <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8010074>.
- 845 Park, J., Kim, D. H., Moon, J. Y., An, J. A., Kim, Y. W., Chung, S. H., et al.
846 (2018). Distribution analysis of twelve mycotoxins in corn and corn-derived
847 products by LC-MS/MS to evaluate the carry-over ratio during wet-milling.
848 *Toxins*, *10*, 319. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins10080319>.
- 849 Pereira, V. L., Fernandes, J. O., & Cunha, S. C. (2014). Mycotoxins in cereals
850 and related foodstuffs: A review on occurrence and recent methods of
851 analysis. *Trends in Food Science and Technology*, *36*, 96–136.
- 852 Pietri, A., Bertuzzi, T., Pallaroni, L., & Piva, G. (2004). Occurrence of
853 mycotoxins and ergosterol in maize harvested over 5 years in Northern Italy.
854 *Food Additives and Contaminants*, *21*, 479–487.
- 855 Pleadin, J., Sokolovic, M., Perši, N., Zadavec, M., Jaki, V., & Vulić, A. (2012).
856 Contamination of maize with deoxynivalenol and zearalenone in Croatia.
857 *Food Control*, *28*, 94-98.
- 858 Pleadin, J., Vulić, A., Perši, N., Škrivanko, M., Capek, B., & Cvetnić, Z. (2015).
859 Annual and regional variations of aflatoxin B1 levels seen in grains and feed
860 coming from Croatian dairy farms over a 5-year period. *Food Control*, *47*,
861 221–225.
- 862 Romera, D., Mateo, E. M., Mateo-Castro, R., Gómez, J. V., Gimeno-
863 Adelantado, & Jiménez, M. (2018). Determination of multiple mycotoxins in
864 feedstuffs by combined use of UPLC–MS/MS and UPLC–QTOF–MS. *Food*
865 *Chemistry*, *267*, 140–148.
- 866 SANTE (2017). Guidance document on analytical quality control and method
867 validation procedures for pesticide residues and analysis in food and feed.
868 SANTE/11813/2017, 21–22 Nov. rev.0.
- 869 Schollenberger, M., Müller, H. M., Ernst, K., Sondermann, S., Liebscher, M.,
870 Schlecker, C., et al. (2012). Occurrence and distribution of 13 trichothecene
871 toxins in naturally contaminated maize plants in Germany. *Toxins*, *4*, 778–
872 787. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins4100778>.
- 873 Schollenberger, M., Müller, H. M., Rühle, M., Suchy, S., Planck, S., & Drochner,
874 W. (2005). Survey of *Fusarium* toxins in foodstuffs of plant origin marketed in

875 Germany. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 97, 317–326.

876 Silva, A. S., Brites, C., Pouca, V. A., Barbosa, J., & Freitas, A. (2019). UHPLC-
877 ToF-MS method for determination of multi-mycotoxins in maize:
878 Development and validation. *Current Research in Food Science*, 1, 1–7.

879 Smith, M. C., Madec, S., Coton E., & Hymery, N. (2016). Natural co-occurrence
880 of mycotoxins in foods and feeds and their *in vitro* combined toxicological
881 effects. *Toxins*, 8, 94. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins8040094>.

882 Streit, E., Naehrer, K., Rodrigues, I., & Schatzmayr, G. (2012). Mycotoxin
883 occurrence in feed and feed raw materials worldwide: long-term analysis
884 with special focus on Europe and Asia. *Journal of Science of Food and
885 Agriculture*, 93, 2892–2899.

886 Sulyok, M., Berthiller, F., Krska, R., & Schuhmacher, R. (2006). Development
887 and validation of a liquid chromatography/tandem mass spectrometric
888 method for the determination of 39 mycotoxins in wheat and maize. *Rapid
889 Communications in Mass Spectrometry*, 20, 2649–2659.

890 Sulyok, M., Krska, R., & Schuhmacher, R. (2007). Application of a liquid
891 chromatography–tandem mass spectrometric method to multi-mycotoxin
892 determination in raw cereals and evaluation of matrix effects. *Food Additives
893 and Contaminants*, 24, 1184–1195.

894 Sun, G., Wang, S., Hu, X., Su, J., Zhang, Y., Tang, L., et al. (2011). Co-
895 contamination of aflatoxin B1 and fumonisin B1 in food and human dietary
896 exposure in three areas of China. *Food Additives and Contaminants: Part A*
897 28, 461-470.

898 Tangni, E. K., Pussemier, L., & Van Hove, F. (2013). Mycotoxin contaminating
899 maize and grass silages for dairy cattle feeding: current state and
900 challenges. *Journal of Animal Science Advances*, 3, 492–511.

901 Tarazona, A., Mateo, E. M., Gómez, J. V., Romera, D. & Mateo, F. (2020).
902 Potential use of machine learning methods in assessment of *Fusarium
903 culmorum* and *Fusarium proliferatum* growth and mycotoxin production in
904 treatments with antifungal agents. *Fungal Biology* (in press).
905 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.funbio.2019.11.006>.

- 906 Valle-Algarra, F. M., Medina, A., Gimeno-Adelantado, J. V., Llorens, A.,
907 Jiménez, M., & Mateo, R. (2005). Comparative assessment of solid-phase
908 extraction clean-up procedures, GC columns and perfluoroacylation
909 reagents for determination of type B trichothecenes in wheat by GC-ECD.
910 *Talanta*, *66*, 194–201.
- 911 Valle-Algarra, F. M., Mateo-Castro, R., Mateo, E., Gimeno-Adelantado, J. V. &
912 Jiménez, M. (2014). Mycotoxins: Detection and Analysis by Classical
913 Techniques. In C. A., Batt, & M. L. Tortorello, (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Food*
914 *Microbiology*, (pp. 862–868) vol 2. Amsterdam: Elsevier Ltd, Academic
915 Press.
- 916 Van Asselt, E. D., Azambuja, W., Moretti, A., Kastelein, P., De Rijk, T. C.,
917 Stratakou, I., et al. (2012). A Dutch field survey on fungal infection and
918 mycotoxin concentrations in maize. *Food and Additives Contaminants: Part*
919 *A*, *29*, 1556–1565.
- 920 Varga, E., Glauner, T., Köppen, R., Mayer, K., Sulyok, M., Schuhmacher, R., et
921 al. (2012). Stable isotope dilution assay for the accurate determination of
922 mycotoxins in maize by UHPLC-MS/MS. *Analytical and Bioanalytical*
923 *Chemistry*, *402*, 2675–2686.
- 924 Zhang, K., Schaab, M. R., Southwood, G., Tor, E. R., Aston, L. S., Song, W. et
925 al. (2017). A collaborative study: determination of mycotoxins in corn, peanut
926 butter, and wheat flour using stable isotope dilution assay (SIDA) and liquid
927 chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). *Journal of*
928 *Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, *65*, 7138–7152.

929 FIGURE CAPTIONS

930

931 Fig. 1. UPLC-(ESI+)-MS/MS MRM chromatograms of mycotoxin standards
932 added to an extract of blank maize. AFB₁, 2 ng/mL; AFB₂, 2 ng/mL; DON, 250
933 ng/mL; ZEA, 100 ng/mL; OTA, 26 ng/mL; FB₁, 250 ng/mL; FB₂, 125 ng/mL. For
934 each mycotoxin, Q: quantifier ion; q: qualifier ion.

935

936 Fig. 2. UPLC-(ESI+)-MS/MS MRM chromatograms of mycotoxin standards
937 added to an extract of blank maize. T-2, 25 ng/mL; HT-2, 25 ng/mL; AFG₁, 2
938 ng/mL; AFG₂, 2 ng/mL. Q: quantifier ion; q: qualifier ion; q': alternative qualifier
939 ion (not used usually).

940

941 Fig. 3. UPLC-(ESI+)-MS/MS MRM chromatograms of naturally contaminated
942 maize samples containing a) 184 ng AFB₁/g; b) 8.85 ng AFB₂/g; c) 1.74×10³ ng
943 DON/g; d) 1.13×10⁴ ng ZEA/g; e) 5.09×10⁴ ng FB₁/g; f) 1.21×10⁴ ng FB₂/g; g)
944 45.6 ng 3-ADON/g; h)11.7 ng HT-2/g.

945

946 Fig.4. Distribution of the levels of FB₁+FB₂ in samples of maize kernel collected
947 in Spain with concentrations of FB₁ or FB₂ ≥ LOQ in the period 2015-2019.

948

949 Fig. 5. Co-occurrence of mycotoxins at levels ≥ LOQ in samples of maize
950 kernels collected in Spain throughout the years 2015 to 2019. FUM means FB₁
951 and/or FB₂; AF means AFB₁, AFB₂ or AFG₂.

Table 1.

Optimized MS/MS parameters, quantitative daughter ion and assistant qualifier daughter ion utilized and average retention times (t_R)

Mycotoxin	Elemental formula	Base mass (Dalton)	Precursor ion (m/z) (Dalton)	Product ions (m/z) (Dalton)	Cone voltage (V)	Collision energy (eV)	Average t_R (min)	
DON	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₆	296.126	297.0	[M + H] ⁺	231.0 ^a	20	15	2.9
					249.5 ^b	15	10	
3-ADON/ 15-ADON	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₇	338.137	339.1	[M + H] ⁺	231.0 ^a	35	15	4.5
					203.2 ^b	35	12	
AFB ₁	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₆	312.063	313.0	[M + H] ⁺	285.0 ^a	70	25	6.0
					241.0 ^b	70	35	
AFB ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₆	314.079	315.0	[M + H] ⁺	287.0 ^a	70	30	5.7
					259.0 ^b	70	25	
AFG ₁	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₇	328.058	329.0	[M + H] ⁺	243.0 ^a	70	25	5.5
					283.0 ^b	70	25	
AFG ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₇	330.074	331.0	[M + H] ⁺	257.0 ^a	70	30	5.2
					285.2 ^b	70	30	
ZEA	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₅	318.147	319.0	[M + H] ⁺	187.0 ^a	20	20	8.4
					185.0 ^b	20	25	
OTA	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ ClNO ₆	403.082	404.0	[M + H] ⁺	239.1 ^a	25	20	8.6
					221.2 ^b	40	30	
HT-2 toxin	C ₂₂ H ₃₂ O ₈	424.210	442.0	[M + NH ₄] ⁺	263.0 ^a	20	15	7.1
					215.0 ^b	20	15	
T-2 toxin	C ₂₄ H ₃₄ O ₉	466.5	484.0	[M + NH ₄] ⁺	305.4 ^a	20	15	7.8
					245.2 ^b	20	15	
FB ₁	C ₃₄ H ₅₉ NO ₁₅	721.388	723.0	[M + H] ⁺	334.0 ^a	50	40	7.7
					352.0 ^b	50	40	
FB ₂	C ₃₄ H ₅₉ NO ₁₄	705.394	706.0	[M + H] ⁺	336.0 ^a	50	40	9.1
					354.3 ^b	50	40	

^a: quantifier ion; ^b: assistant qualifier ion

Table 2

Limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ), mean recoveries and mean relative standard deviations of recoveries under conditions of repeatability (RSD_r) for mycotoxin standards added to blank maize kernels at four levels and analyzed by UPLC-(ESI +)-MS/MS.

Mycotoxin	LOD (ng/g)	LOQ (ng/g)	Mean recovery (%)	Mean RSD_r (%)
FB1	6.0	18.0	95.5	4.3
FB2	3.0	9.0	96.2	4.1
DON	12	36	83.0	8.5
3-ADON	15	45	85.6	6.7
ZEA	12	36	95.4	4.4
AFB1	0.28	0.84	98.3	6.2
AFB2	0.10	0.30	103.4	6.5
AFG1	1.2	3.6	102.4	5.4
AFG2	0.7	2.1	95.2	7.5
T-2	1.7	5.1	96.8	7.9
HT-2	2.2	6.6	94.4	5.8
OTA	2.7	8.1	99.2	5.4

Table 3

Occurrence of mycotoxins in maize kernel samples from Spanish suppliers in the period 2015-2019 (N = 98).

Mycotoxin	No of samples with undetectable levels	No of samples with levels between LOD and LOQ	Number and % of samples with mycotoxin levels > LOQ ^a	Range of mycotoxin levels in positive samples (ng/g)	Mean / median ^c (ng/g)	EU maximum permitted level (ng/g)	Number and % of samples with mycotoxin levels exceeding the EU limits
FB ₁	26	2	70 (71.4)	26.0–5.09×10 ⁴	4700 / 1080	–	–
FB ₂	42	1	55 (56.1)	12.2–1.21×10 ⁴	1317 / 374.3	–	–
FB ₁ +FB ₂	–	–	–	26.0–6.31×10 ⁴	5734 / 1306	4000	20 (20.4%)
DON	59	8	31 (31.6)	73.5–1737	422 / 180	1750	0 (0%)
3-ADON ^b	91	2	5 (5.1)	45.6–104.7	66.3 / 63.9	–	–
ZEA	63	11	24 (24.5)	55.0–1.13×10 ⁴	837 / 110.3	350	6 (6.1%)
AFB ₁	51	38	9 (9.2)	0.87–124.1	26 / 1.55	5	3 (3%)
AFB ₂	79	10	9 (9.2)	0.31–8.85	1.29 / 0.33	–	–
AFG ₁	94	4	–	–	–	–	–
AFG ₂	88	6	2 (2)	4.5–5.6	5.05 / 5.05	–	–
Sum of AFBs	–	–	–	0.31–133	–	10	3 (3%)
T-2	73	20	5 (5.1)	5.8–13.8	9.5 / 8.6	–	–
HT-2	75	18	5 (5.1)	7.1–24.3	13 / 11.7	–	–
T-2+HT-2	–	–	–	12.9–26.8	21 / 20.3	200 ^d	–
OTA	98	–	–	–	–	5	–

a. % samples are between parentheses.

b. Includes the concentration of possible 15-ADON (there is no EU limit).

c. Average and median of values ≥ LOQ. For FB₁ + FB₂ and T-2 + HT-2: values exceeding the sum of LOQ of the individual toxins.

d. Recommended maximum limit.

Table 4

Year-to-year variation from 2015 to 2019 of mycotoxin contamination at quantifiable levels in samples of Spanish maize kernels. AFG₁ and OTA levels are omitted as their concentrations were always < LOQ.

Mycotoxin	Year				
	2015 (N ^a = 10)	2016 (N = 22)	2017 (N = 26)	2018 (N = 21)	2019 (N = 19)
	n ^b / Mean / Range ^c	n / Mean / Range	n / Mean / Range	n / Mean / Range	n / Mean / Range
FB ₁	6 / 920 / 43.0–3754	15 / 8332 / 27.5–3.46×10 ⁴	19 / 7715 / 26.0–5.09×10 ⁴	14 / 2657 / 39.9–1.71×10 ⁴	16 / 920 / 29.0–3841
FB ₂	5 / 354 / 18.0–878.8	11 / 2188 / 57.9–1.04×10 ⁴	15 / 2296 / 12.2–1.21×10 ⁴	12 / 613 / 17.5–4040	12 / 402 / 12.4–1170
FB ₁ +FB ₂	6 / 1214 / 61.0–4634	15 / 9936 / 27.5–4.50×10 ⁴	19 / 9523 / 26.0–6.31×10 ⁴	14 / 3183 / 39.9–2.11×10 ⁴	16 / 1221 / 29.0–4825
DON	2 / 115 / 91.0–131	15 / 394.4 / 73.5–1327	6 / 129.4 / 85.0–175	5 / 881 / 57.3–1737	3 / 582 / 123–1194
3-ADON	–	1 / 45.6	–	2 / 65 / 63.9–66.3	2 / 78.0 / 51.2–104.7
ZEA	3 / 73.3 / 75.0–100	10 / 1493 / 73.4–1.13×10 ⁴	3 / 115.2 / 55.0–210.8	3 / 1335 / 60.5–3274	5 / 110.6 / 55.0–248.0
AFB ₁	1 / 0.93	3 / 1.62 / 1.42–1.90	2 / 73.0 / 22.0–124.1	2 / 40.6 / 0.87–80.4	1 / 0.91
AFB ₂	1 / 0.35	3 / 0.40 / 0.31–0.49	2 / 4.6 / 0.33–8.85	2 / 0.315 / 0.31–0.32	1 / 0.33
AFG ₂	–	–	–	1 / 5.58	1 / 4.8
Sum of AFs	1 / 1.28	5 / 0.31 / 0.31–1.90	3 / 77.5 / 0.33–133	4 / 40.6 / 0.31–80.4	3 / 3.00 / 1.24–4.8
T-2	–	–	–	3 / 8.39 / 5.84–12.1	2 / 11.2 / 8.62–13.8
HT-2	–	–	1 / 24.3	2 / 7.87 / 7.08–8.65	2 / 12.35 / 11.7–13.0
T-2+HT-2	–	–	1 / 24.3	3 / 13.6 / 12.1–15.9	2 / 23.5 / 20.3–26.8

^a : Number of analyzed samples.

^b : Number of samples with mycotoxin concentrations ≥ LOQ; For sums: N^o of samples with all the added concentrations ≥ LOQ.

^c : Mean / Range of mycotoxin concentrations ≥ LOQ (ng/g).

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

AFB1

AFB2

DON

ZEA

FB1

FB2

3ADON

HT2

Figure 4

Figure 5

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Andrea Tarazona: Investigation, Methodology. **José V. Gómez:** Investigation, Methodology. **Misericordia Jiménez:** Conceptualization, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Resources, Writing - review & editing.

Fernando Mateo: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Software, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **David Romera:** Investigation, Methodology. **Eva M. Mateo:** Conceptualization, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Data curation, Visualization, Validation, Supervision.